

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PROSTHETICS FOR PATIENTS WITH ALLERGIES TO ACRYLATES

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Abstract

Despite the available and constantly progressively modified materials necessary for the manufacture of modern types of orthopedic structures used to restore the integrity of the dentition, removable dentures are an integral part and still remain a relevant alternative due to their economic availability, speed of production, replacement and repair among older patients [2, 5]. The main types of removable dentures with rigid bases used in the practice of an orthopedic dentist are essentially combined irritants, since they contain several different types of chemical compounds in the structure, be it base plastics, artificial teeth of plastics of other compositions or ceramics, metal alloys of cast bases or wire bent clasps

Keywords: removable dentures, negative reactions, silicone lining material.

Pathological changes when using removable dentures made of acrylic plastics occur due to the effect on the human body of surface erosion products and the elimination of components of acrylic plastics, which include methyl methacrylate, compounds of methacrylic and acrylic acids, plasticizers, dyes and catalysts. Erosion of plastic occurs under the influence of a number of reasons, including incomplete binding of the monomer during the polymerization process, selective extraction of components, and chemical and mechanical effects that occur during the operation of the prosthesis.

Pathological symptoms are most often localized in the area of the prosthetic bed. Taking this into account, in order to eliminate manifestations of intolerance to acrylic plastics, a layer of elastic plastic of a different chemical nature is applied to the inner surface of the denture bases. For patients with intolerance to acrylic plastics, elastic silicone materials with high and low temperature vulcanization are recommended. Although silicone elastic materials have less adhesion to a rigid acrylic base compared to acrylic elastomers, they retain elasticity for a long time, have minimal volumetric changes, and have virtually no toxic effects in the oral cavity.

According to a previously known method, before forming an elastic silicone layer on manufactured prostheses, it is necessary to prepare a rigid base, which consists of forming a chamber corresponding to the thickness of the layer of applied lining material, retreating 2-3 mm from the border along the inner surface of the prosthesis.

However, in patients with symptoms of acrylate intolerance, burning, petechial hemorrhages, and hyperemia are often observed not only in the area of the prosthetic bed, but also in the area of the borders of the prosthetic bases. With the traditional method of applying elastic materials, the edge of the prosthesis adjacent to the transitional fold remains uninsulated.

The purpose of the study is to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment with removable dentures in patients with intolerance to the structural materials of removable dentures. Research objectives: to develop a method for applying elastic plastic to reduce the influence of acrylic plastic components on the tissues of the prosthetic bed, to evaluate the results of the proposed method in the long term of using prostheses.

Material and methods. The elastic layer was applied to 19 patients, on previously made 29 dentures made of acrylic plastic (17 dentures on the upper jaw, 12 on the lower jaw), of which 19 were plate dentures with partial absence of teeth, and 10 with complete absence of teeth. 24 prostheses were made from colorless plastic. The manufactured prostheses met the requirements. Fixation and stabilization of the prostheses were assessed as satisfactory. The period of use of prostheses before the onset of intolerance varied from 4 months to 2-3 years. Previously, in other dental clinics, all patients' dentures were repeatedly altered. Subjective and objective manifestations of intolerance did not go away.

To conduct the study, a modern, well-proven low-temperature vulcanization silicone elastomer was used. The elastic layer was replaced every 6 months.

Results. A technique has been developed for applying an elastic silicone layer over the entire inner surface of the removable denture base with a transition to the outer surface within 5 mm. In this case, a two-layer prosthesis base is formed with an "elastic edge" and an optimal thickness of the lining layer of 1 mm.

The preparation of previously manufactured plate dentures was carried out using a spherical bur with a head diameter of 1 mm, which created a groove parallel to the occlusal curve on the outer surface of the removable denture, 5 mm from the edge adjacent to the transitional fold. Then, approximate notches were applied on the inner and outer surfaces of the base within the

groove to control the future thickness of the elastic layer. After that, a layer of hard plastic was removed with a metal cutter. The surface of the formed chamber was processed mechanically using a milling cutter and medium-grain sandpaper, then degreased, dried, and a sublayer (primer) was applied to it.

The prepared elastic material was applied to the previously prepared surface of the prosthesis base, which was inserted into the patient's oral cavity. The formation of the elastic layer on the base of the prosthesis was carried out under the control of central occlusion. The elastic edge of the removable denture was adjusted before the final vulcanization of the elastic material by simulating chewing movements. Next, using a sharp instrument (scalpel, scissors), excess material was removed.

In two patients, after 3 months, the elastic layer detached from the acrylic base from the outer surface of the prosthesis, which was a consequence of non-compliance with the recommendations for the care of prostheses.

All patients are followed up for 3 years. During this period, no subjective or objective manifestations of intolerance to basic materials were identified.

Conclusion.

The proposed features of the preparation of hard bases and the method of forming an elastic layer in the oral cavity in case of intolerance to acrylic plastics gave a positive result. The use of removable dentures with two-layer bases makes it possible to reduce the influence of acrylic plastic components on the tissues of the prosthetic bed and transitional fold, achieve a more uniform distribution of chewing pressure, reduce pain and

discomfort in people with unfavorable conditions of the prosthetic bed, including those with intolerance to acrylic plastics

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